

Computationally Efficient Finite Element Platform for Modelling Automated Fibre Placement

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Background

- In an effort to increase composite production rate and reduce costs, the industry is turning towards automated manufacturing, like automated fibre placement.
- The method consists of automatically depositing strips of prepreg tows onto a mould using a computer-controlled robot.

Schematic of the AFP layup process [1].

Background

- Set-up of AFP is based on engineering judgement and time-consuming trials.
- Ability to predict as-manufactured geometry would allow for a clearer assessment between part quality, conformity and productivity.
- Linking Process-Material-Quality.

Research Aims and Objectives

- The aim of the project was the development of a numerically efficient framework, which captures the process-quality interaction.
- To develop physics-based simulation platform to investigate material-process interaction during AFP and enable exploration of the entire processing window.

State-of-the-Art

- Includes a sequentially coupled FE model, adapted from TUM [2], with a experimentally characterised prepreg model [3].
- Impact of process parameters on preform geometry can be directly simulated.
- Computationally expensive, limited scalability with increasing ply count.

Computational Efficiency

- Constraining inconsequential deformations.
 - Rigid parts.
 - Containing undesired dynamic motion.
- Computationally efficient material model.
 - Homogenisation of substrate bulk.

Model cut-out with parts in white being rigid.

Comparison of the predictions for wrinkle formation in severely tapered laminate made by the ply-by-ply and the kinematic enrichment approaches [4].

Numerical Model

- The viscoelastic prepreg material model captures the compaction behaviour which leads to excess length generation.
- The material model was implemented as a UMAT subroutine for Abaqus/STANDARD.

Material characterisation workflow comprising of experimental program, parameter extraction and simulation [3].

Numerical Model

- Current state-of-the-art AFP platform is built on ABAQUS, and includes:
 - Isothermal STANDARD model.
 - Linked with AFP power curves.
 - On-the-fly substrate bulk homogenisation.
 - Prepreg and roller material models characterised over a wide range of processing conditions[3].

Visual representation of isothermal model with homogenised substrate.

Empirical nip-point temperature map along with experimentally obtained fitting data points [5].

Computational Efficiency

- Computational cost of a single 200mm tape layup:
 - Sequentially coupled (TUM): **24255s.**
 - Sequentially coupled, characterised material models (UoB): **44960s.**
 - Isothermal, fully deformable: **1922s.**
 - Isothermal, constrained deformations: **1074s.**

Comparison of run times for various AFP models, depositing 15 plies at 20mm/s under 425N of compaction force and 394W lamp power.

Numerical Study

- Seven layup cases were investigated with the following range of processing parameters:
 - Lamp power: 131 – 394W
 - Compaction force: 120 – 425N
 - Layup speed: 20 – 60mm/s
- Fifteen 0° IM7/8552 plies consisting of eight 6.35mm (¼in) tows were laid up at the NCC [5].

Numerical Study

- Under the specified process range and preform thickness, slight variation in compaction is observed.
- Preform compaction increases with:
 - Increasing compaction force.

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- Under the specified process range and preform thickness, slight variation in compaction is observed.
- Preform compaction increases with:
 - Increasing compaction force.
 - Increasing lamp power.
 - Reducing layup speed.

Ongoing Activities

- Further improvements, which include:
 - On-the-fly length generation.
 - Through-thickness preform temperature variation.
- Introduction of complex layup paths and tool surfaces.
- Further tuning of platform to improve accuracy.

Conclusion

- Capable of capturing the influence of wide range of processing conditions on conformance.
- The process map can give guidance to current AFP projects or be used as a first approximation.
- Future work includes validation, inclusion of material variability and smart process map exploration.

Distribution of the fibre volume fraction [6].

Measured uncured ply thickness (a) and the resulting ply thickness (b) of the 4mm laminate subject to the predefined autoclave cycle [6].

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